

Add-ons and “therapeutic illusion”

First of all, what are Add-ons?

They are optional additional treatments, also referred to as 'supplementary', 'adjuvants' or 'embryology treatments' offered by fertility clinics claiming to improve the chances of having a baby through assisted reproduction technologies. Of course, each of these treatments is added to the fertility cycle for an additional cost, varying from 100 euros to thousands of euros. Nevertheless, the evidence to support the reliability and effectiveness of these treatments is often missing or non-reliable.

Due to assisted reproduction technologies' inevitable low success rate, clinics often use add-ons to create a customer loyalty program to keep patients as clients. This way, patients enter a vicious emotional cycle that pushes them to try again and again when the standard treatment has failed, with different add-ons. What drives them is the hope of success.

It is essential to ascertain whether these add-on therapies' improvement compared to the standard procedure is based on scientific evidence and whether their success rates are true to their promise. In the ethical reflections on assisted human reproduction, there is a term called "*therapeutic illusion*", which refers to this reality.

Many organizations, such as B2-InF's consortium partner **Fertility Europe**, has long been fighting to improve the information provided to patients in order to avoid falling into this illusion.

The lack of transparency and regulation is part of the core reasons why the B2-InF project exists, which is interested in analyzing the information that clinics are offering to society and improving them according to society's needs and expectations, also allowing governments to act well informed.